

PIDGraph

PID Graph

Partners working on this component

Component Overview

The PIDGraph services are designed to facilitate the exposure and usage of Persistent Identifier (PID) metadata and connections, centered around a trusted source - in this instance, the core data of the graph is made up of Digital Object Identifier (DOI) metadata held by DataCite, one of the main DOI Registration Agencies (RAs), and the network of the graph is built around the relationships connection one DOI to another, and also outwards from DOIs to other established and trusted PIDs within the research community, including Open Researcher and Contributor IDs (ORCID) for people, and Research Organisation Registry (ROR) identifiers for institutions, as well as domain specific persistent identifiers such as zbMATH Article Identifiers.

During FAIRCORE4EOSC, work was done to enhance the performance and functionalities of the APIs available for accessing the data, to generate and publish data files of the node metadata and vertices, to develop a statistics reporting tool, and to ingest new data into the graph from project partners.

The PIDGraph helps researchers by exposing the metadata of research outputs for reuse and aggregation by other EOSC partners and services, as well as the wider scholarly community. The addition of datasets containing the links between PIDs enable tracking and reporting of citations and references, alongside other relationships between research outputs.

By leveraging a common schema, the data is easily ingested and by using machine-readable APIs such as GraphQL, integration can be automated, ensuring a streamlined method of working with the PIDGraph data.

Functionalities

The PIDGraph provides several APIs for accessing the data, including a REST API, a GraphQL API, and an OAI-PMH API. In addition, the graph data is regularly published in two datasets, one comprising the metadata for nodes in the graph, and the other containing the vertices of the graph. These services are built on top of DataCite's existing open infrastructure and data.

Access to the graph data is also possible through the web frontend of DataCite Commons, allowing interactive browsing through the data and the visualisation of relationships and metadata aggregations.

Enhancement of the graph data is achieved by the ingestion of metadata from external sources, via dedicated APIs and the common OAI-PMH framework, and the inclusion of PID to PID links from this metadata into the graph.

Usage Statistics reporting for DOIs is made via regular COUNTER-compliant reports to a dedicated service, or by using a JavaScript widget directly on the resource's landing page to submit real-time usage statistics to the PIDGraph.

Impact

By increasing the availability and interoperability of PID metadata, the PIDGraph services help to increase the use and utility of scholarly research outputs and enrich systems and services in the wider community.

By publishing data on the relationships between PIDs, the availability of citation information is enhanced, providing benefit to researchers and institutions.

By ingesting data from other trusted sources, the size and scope of the graph is increased, producing downstream benefits to users of the graph data when working with the PIDGraph services.

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